

Reproducibility Study - Context and Attribute-Aware Sequential Recommendation via Cross-Attention Rashed *et al.* (2022)

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1. Abstract

There are numerous difficulties in reproducing experiments in the field of data science. This is due to several reasons, such as lack of access to the code, data used or preprocessing steps, insufficient reporting of factors and different hardware and software configurations such as the operating system, versions of programming languages, packages and libraries (even outdated libraries), hyper-parameters, and different random seeds initialization used, among others.

In this report, as part of the final project for the "Experiment Design for Data Science" course at TU Wien, the reproducibility of three chosen papers were evaluated and attempted to replicate one of them.

2. Introduction

Reproducibility is essential for scientific findings, as it ensures that results can be replicated in scientific practice. The reproducibility of a paper was investigated in the field of data science, with a specific focus on the paper "Context and Attribute-Aware Sequential Recommendation via Cross-Attention". Despite the availability of a GitHub repository with code and instructions, we found that the code needed to be modified before it could be run. However, after making the necessary adjustments, we were able to reproduce the results of 2 of the 4 data sets from the original paper. One of the biggest problems in reproducing the results is the computation power. We were not able to run the scripts in our local machines. Therefore, Google Collab was used. However, due to the large size of the data sets, we still run out of computational units.

The report consists of 6 different sections. Section 3 and 4 contains the summary of the paper, the results of which we have to reproduce, and the related work, respectively. In section 5, the experimental setup of the paper is examined. In section 6, the reproduction results are presented and in section 7, our critique about these results is included. Finally, in section 8 an overall conclusion is presented.

3. Paper Summary

This paper presents a new model called CARCA for recommending items to users. The model takes into account both the user's context and the attributes of the items being recommended. Current methods either ignore these factors or only consider one of them, which limits their effectiveness. CARCA uses multi-head self-attention blocks to extract features from user profiles and item attributes and predict scores for items. It also uses cross-attention between all items in the user's profile and the items being recommended

to predict final scores. This allows CARCA to better consider the correlation between old and recent items in the user’s profile. The model was tested on four real-world datasets and was found to significantly outperform other methods, achieving improvements of up to 53% in performance measures such as NDCG and Hit-Ratio. Additionally, CARCA was found to perform better than image-based recommendation systems even when using image attributes in a black-box fashion.

4. Related Work

There have been many context- and attribute-aware recommendation models that have been developed and have shown consistent performance on a wide range of recommendation tasks, such as next-item recommendation, rating prediction and click-through rate prediction. Context-aware models can be divided into two main categories: those that use contextual features and additional attributes in a single vector format and those that use time and the sequential order of user interactions (time-aware models). They are able to achieve better performance because they can capture the high variability of user behavior and anticipate their next preferences. On the other hand, attribute-aware models use additional item and user attributes to generate rich latent representations and provide better recommendations, which is especially useful in settings with rich item attributes and unique item recommendations.

5. Experimental Setup

CARCA captures the user profiles’ dynamic nature and contextual changes seamlessly alongside any available item attributes. The authors look into a sequential problem which considers all users to have profiles that contain the sequence of their previously interacted items along with their attributes and their interactions’ contextual features, such as timestamps. To capture the evolving users’ behaviour existing in their profiles, their model utilizes two analogous multi-head self attention based branches. The left branch is a series of self-attention blocks that extract the user’s profile’s contextual information and item features, while the right branch consists of a multi-head cross-attention block that captures the influence of the left branch’s profile-level features on the target item’s attributes and contextual features. The goal of this item recommendation task was to rank a target list of items based on their likelihood of being interacted with by a target user u at a time $t + 1$ while similarly considering attributes and contextual features existing at that time point.

According to the training protocol used, for each user the authors excluded his last interaction and converted the user profile sequence into a fixed-length input list of items $P^u = \{i_1^P, i_2^P, i_{p_t^u-1}^P\}$ by using truncation or padding. This list of input items was constructed by combining a list of positive items and another list of negative items with equal length, the latter composed randomly and given the same contextual features as their corresponding positive ones.

The authors conduct multiple experiments to evaluate the performance of the CARCA model with other state-of-the-art recommendation and image-based recommendation system models. They evaluate the performance of CARCA based on four diverse and widely used real-world data sets extracted from Amazon.com, such as:

- (i) *Men*: contains all items belonging to men’s clothing including subcategories (gloves, scarves,). The item attributes of this data set are image-based features extracted by a pre-trained ResNet50 model

- (ii) *Fashion*: contains all items that belong to six fashion categories(men/women’s tops,bottoms,shoes).The item attributes are also extracted the same way as for Men data set
- (iii) *Games*: contains all items belonging to video games category. The item attributes in this data set are price, fine-grained categories,and the item’s brand. Most item attributes, in contrast to the first data sets, are discrete and categorical variables
- (iv) *Beauty*: contains all items that belong to the beauty category. The item attributes in this data set are fine-grained categories and the item’s brand. All attributes are discrete and categorical variables

In order to make their model comparable to S^3 Rec which only uses categorical attributes, the authors discretized all real-valued input features of the *Men*,*Fashion* and *Games* data sets into different levels. For evaluating CARCA and other baseline models, the leave-one-out protocol was used, in which two last interactions of each users were held out for validation and test while the rest of the interactions was used for training. The hyper-parameters of the model were tuned on the validation set using grid search.

To evaluate the performance, the authors sampled 100 negative items that were not interacted with by the user, gave them all the same context as their corresponding positive test item, and rank the positive test item among them. At the end, for each user, the authors truncated the ranked list at a threshold value of 10. They measured the overall quality by using average Hit-Ration(HR) and the Normalized Discounted Cumulative Gain (NDCG) among users. In order to ensure the statistical significance of the results, the authors repeated the evaluation process multiple times with different sets of random negative items, and reported the average metrics across the different runs. Moreover, they utilized a paired t-test for measuring significance.

The comparison results shown in the following table, show that CARCA with cross attention significantly outperforms all state-of-the-art context, sequential and attribute-aware models on various settings and with different item attributes types. As stated in the paper, CARCA is also able to achieve improvements up to 53% when compared against SSE-PT, because it utilizes the full pre-computed item’s image features on *Men* and *Fashion* data sets without needing any data discretization, unlike S^3 Rec which only handles categorical attributes.

Model	ATT	CXT	SEQ	Men		Fashion		Games		Beauty	
				HR@10	NDCG@10	HR@10	NDCG@10	HR@10	NDCG@10	HR@10	NDCG@10
Random				0.098	0.044	0.099	0.045	0.100	0.045	0.099	0.045
TopPop				0.415	0.269	0.407	0.262	0.519	0.314	0.451	0.261
EASE [22]				0.193	0.133	0.213	0.146	0.623	0.465	0.299	0.222
GraphRec [16]	✓			0.374	0.219	0.419	0.244	0.613	0.400	0.435	0.273
DeepFM [6]	✓	✓		0.334	0.237	0.283	0.185	0.736	0.494	0.464	0.266
SASRec [12]		✓	✓	0.397	0.259	0.381	0.245	0.742	0.541	0.485	0.322
OAR [26]		✓	✓	0.355	0.225	0.340	0.214	0.704	0.496	0.485	0.329
TiSASRec [13]		✓	✓	0.333	0.194	0.384	0.234	0.748	0.533	0.492	0.333
BERT4Rec [23]		✓	✓	0.315	0.193	0.328	0.209	0.705	0.509	0.478	0.318
SSE-SASRec [27]		✓	✓	0.397	0.257	0.385	0.248	0.754	0.549	0.481	0.330
SSE-PT [28]		✓	✓	0.397	0.258	0.381	0.246	0.748(0.775)	0.545(0.566)	0.443(0.502)	0.302(0.337)
S^3 Rec [36]	✓	✓	✓	0.365	0.238	0.367	0.239	0.765	0.549	0.538	0.371
SASRec++ (Our extension)	✓	✓	✓	0.500	0.315	0.546	0.344	0.752	0.533	0.545	0.351
CARCA (w/o CA) (Ours)	✓	✓	✓	0.521	0.322	0.568	0.359	0.738	0.517	0.556	0.358
CARCA (Ours)	✓	✓	✓	0.550*	0.349*	0.591*	0.381*	0.782*	0.573*	0.579*	0.396
Improv. vs best baseline (%)				38.65	35.87	53.71	53.24	2.20	4.38	7.70	6.74
Improv. vs SASRec++ (%)				10.09	10.79	8.25	10.67	3.96	7.64	6.31	12.95

(*) Significantly outperforms the best baseline at the 0.01 levels.
Published results of SSE-PT are indicated in parentheses.

The performance of the CARCA model was also compared against multiple state-of-the-art image-based recommendation system models on the *Fashion* data set. For evaluating the models, the authors sampled 500 negative items instead of 100 and used area under the curve (AUC) instead of HitRatio. This procedure allowed them to compare CARCA against the published results of the baseline models, VBPR, JRL, SAERS,etc.

According to the paper, CARCA was able to outperform all image-based recommendation models.

Model	NDCG@10	AUC
Random	0.012	0.501
TopPop	0.125	0.595
VBPR [8]	0.085	0.771
JRL [33]	0.127	0.771
SAERS [11]	<u>0.171</u>	<u>0.816</u>
CARCA	0.184	0.841
Improvement over best baseline (%)	7.54	3.03

For measuring the impact of the item attributes and the contextual features on CARCA’s performance, the authors conducted a comparative study between different CARCA versions that utilize different combinations of attributes and features. The authors show that the impact of item attributes and contextual features are different across the data sets. On the *Men* and *Fashion* data sets, item attributes and their image features have a significant effect on the performance, while contextual features had a lower impact. On the other hand, contextual features had a higher impact on CARCA’s performance on the *Games* data set than item attributes because video games are more volatile than clothes for example, as they are more susceptible to critics and the satisfaction of their player-bases.

Moreover, the authors conducted multiple experiments on the *Men* data set to measure the impact of each of the model components and to compare different possible configurations of the CARCA architecture. Again, CARCA outperformed different versions of itself, such as CARCA with additive residual connections, CARCA with input vectors concatenated in one long feature vector, etc.

6. Reproduced Results

As mentioned in the previous sections, both data and the code are available for conducting and reproducing the results of this paper. The aim of reproducing the results of this paper is to confirm the validity and reliability of scientific findings. Furthermore, we are interested in proving the hypothesis of this paper, that CARCA model accurately predicts and recommends items on 4 different databases and outperforms most of the state-of-the-art models.

With the code available, we created a python environment, via Google Colab Pro as it offered a 64 GB RAM, NVIDIA V100 GPU and around 100 computing units that allowed us to successfully reproduce some of the results, as our local machines did not have the needed capacity to deal with the large amount of data used in this paper.

One of the adjustments that we had to take care of before trying to reproduce the results, is the versioning of Tensorflow. The CARCA paper suggested using Tensorflow version 1, but it was no longer supported by Google Colab. For this reason, we shifted to using the second version of TensorFlow.

The next step was to start running the model on the given datasets. First we tried to run the given CARCA algorithm first on the Fashion dataset, but we failed to reproduce the result due to the lack of computing power. Our simple calculations showed that it would need approximately 14 hours to reproduce the results on the Fashion dataset, and it was impossible for our resources, as we were only given 100 computational units and a maximum running time of 12 hours on Google Colab Pro. On the other hand, we

considered running a simpler model with a reduced dataset, but this was impossible too, because of the explainability issues of the datasets. The given datasets lack adequate documentation to explain the numbers in the datasets which did not enable us to understand what they are made of. Additionally, some parts of the used datasets can not be transformed into a readable and understandable file, and thus can not be reduced in size.

We faced the same problems when trying to run the beauty dataset, and finally failed to reproduce the published results of this paper.

On the contrary, since the Games and Men datasets, are the ones smaller in size in comparison to the other two, we managed to run the algorithm and train both of them in 800 Epochs and finally retrieve the results of an NDCG@10: 0.5432 and HR@10: 0.7457 for the Games dataset and NDCG@10: 0.3164 and HR@10: 0.4991 for the Men dataset. The summary results are presented in the table below:

Dataset \ Metric	Reproduced		Paper		% change	
	NDCG@10	HR@10	NDCG@10	HR@10	NDCG@10	HR@10
Games	0.5432	0.7457	0.573	0.782	-5.2	-4,6
Men	0.3164	0.4991	0.349	0.550	-9.3	-9.2

As can be seen from the table, the dataset that have performed better and has reproduced more similar result to the ones of the paper, is the Games dataset with a percentage change in the accuracy metrics of around 5%.

7. Critique

The biggest missing of the paper to make it reproduceable is the inclusion of an adequate documentation of the datasets. As the context files, that are used to build up the model are neither mentioned in the readme file nor in the paper itself, it is impossible to transform them to humanly readable files. This would be necessary to reduce the size of the contextual files to run the code with fewer entries and therefore with a smaller model. Running the code for the two files with the RAM and graphics card we could access, is therefore impossible.

The description of the dataset files also lack in detail. The paper does not mention the meaning of the numbers in the datasets, which make the statistical result not interpretable as any kind of context information is missing. At least in the readme file there should be a clear explanation of the input data.

As mentioned before, rerunning the program and verifying the statistical and contextual results is not possible due to this lacks for two datasets with the limited RAM we have access to.

8. Conclusion

As our reproducibility check shows the RAM and the graphics card we have available is not enough to rebuild the given model reproduce all tests of the paper. Two datasets have an enormous amount of a context dictionary file, which makes it impossible to do a rerun. Taking a subset for simplification is, due to the lack of documentation and our computational power, not possible either. The two datasets that where small enough to reproduce the results of the given experiment were not exactly the same as in the paper, but quite near to them. This means that the our rebuilt CARCA model performs better than most of the other tested and compared to model cited in the paper.

REFERENCES

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